

Discrete and Finite Element Models for the mechanics of unreinforced and reinforced masonry arches

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Abstract. In this work, the behavior of masonry arches, without and with reinforcements, is investigated by means of three different numerical models. On one hand, a discrete element model based on rigid blocks and elastic-plastic interfaces is extended to the case of masonry arches; on the other hand, a standard heterogeneous Finite Element Model is adopted for a detailed micro-modelling of arch voussoirs, joints, and reinforcements. Furthermore, an analytic numerical model is taken in consideration for validating the numerical results. The aim of the work is the comparison and validation of the numerical Finite and Discrete Element models, together with the evaluation of the effectiveness of such models in representing the strengthening effects.

Introduction

Masonry arches represent one of the most important and complex structural elements that can be built with natural or artificial blocks. The assessment of their behavior has received new interest from the community of architects and civil engineers, with particular attention to limit analysis, thanks to the huge contributions by Heyman [1]. Considering the typical pattern of the stones or clay bricks that compose the load-bearing part of arches and vaults, Discrete Element Models (DEMs) are frequently adopted for assessing arch structural behavior [2], since they allow to model each voussoir and the corresponding contacts. Masonry arches are often studied by means of analytical and numerical limit analysis approaches, with the latter that successfully adopt the hypothesis of rigid blocks or rigid elements for defining collapse mechanisms [3]. In recent works dealing with masonry arch bridges, combined Finite-Discrete Element Models (FEM-DEM) were adopted and compared with limit analysis results [4], whereas standard Finite Element Models (FEMs) were adopted with proper homogenization procedures [5]. For restoration purposes and in order to allow masonry arches to stand both increasing vertical loads and/or seismic actions, strengthening interventions are often performed. Fiber-Reinforced-Polymers (FRP) are frequently applied to arch extrados or intrados, in order to increase the capacity of the arch [6-8].

This work deals with the assessment of the behavior of masonry arches, both unreinforced and reinforced, by means of two numerical models and an analytical model. An existing Discrete Element Model (DEM) based on rigid blocks and elastoplastic interfaces, originally introduced for modelling masonry panels having regular texture [9, 10], is here extended to the case of masonry arches in plane state. A heterogeneous FEM with standard quadrilateral elements and zero-thickness interface elements is also considered for calibrating DEM elastic and inelastic parameters. Such approach dedicated to DEM calibration with respect to other existing and commercial DE and FE

models, was performed in the past for in-plane loaded masonry panels [12]. Furthermore, an analytic model of a circular arch without and with a reinforcement along extrados is developed for a further validation of the proposed numerical models. Numerical tests take into account an existing case study [13] already adopted for validating and comparing other numerical approaches.

Numerical and analytical models for masonry arches

Discrete Element Model. The original discrete model introduced by Cecchi and Sab [9] and already extended to the field of material nonlinearity [10] and random or quasi-periodic texture [11] is further extended to the case of blocks and interfaces having a generic position and orientation, with the main purpose of modelling the plane section of a masonry arch or a masonry vault. Analysis is carried on in a linearized two-dimensional (2D) framework, with 2D plane stress hypothesis. Blocks are considered as rigid bodies, whereas the elastic and inelastic behavior of the system is lumped at interface or joint level. Dry or mortar joints are modeled as elastic-plastic interfaces, which follow a Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. Furthermore, the reinforcements applied along arch intrados and/or extrados are modelled as elements connected with the existing blocks. Considering two quadrilateral blocks connected by an interface (Fig. 1a) representing two generic voussoirs of a masonry arch, the displacements of the model are given by the rigid body motions of each block, namely the in-plane translations of each block center and the rotation of each block ω_3 with respect to its center: $\mathbf{q} = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ \omega_3\}^T$. The joint between the blocks is considered as a one-dimensional interface, and the relative displacements between the connected blocks are assumed as deformation measure. Due to the generic orientation of the interface, highlighted by its inclination θ with respect to the horizontal axis (Fig. 1), the relative displacements at interface level (local) - relative normal and shear displacements and relative rotation- $\mathbf{d}_{loc} = \{d_n \ d_s \ \delta\}^T$ are defined in terms of block (global) displacements by means of a rotation matrix and by a compatibility matrix [10] collecting the relative distances of each block center with respect to interface center in the global coordinates system (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1 – Discrete Element Model: (a) two generic blocks in contact; (b) interface actions.

Model deformability and nonlinearity are lumped at interface level by means of elastic-plastic laws. Actions at interface level (local) -a shear action, a normal action and a moment- $\mathbf{f}_{loc} = \{f_n \ f_s \ m\}^T$ (Fig. 1b), initially depend linearly on interface relative displacements, by means of an interface stiffness matrix $\mathbf{f}_{loc} = \mathbf{K}_{loc} \mathbf{d}_{loc}$ collecting shear, normal and bending stiffness: $\mathbf{K}_{loc} = \text{diag}\{k_n \ k_s \ k_r\}$. The material nonlinearity is guaranteed by limiting interface actions with a Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion and a tensile strength criterion. Interfaces representing reinforcements and contacts between blocks and reinforcement can follow different criteria, namely a maximum tensile strength for reinforcing elements, and a shear-bond strength for contacts between blocks and reinforcements.

Heterogeneous Finite Element Model. In order to model a masonry arch with a better detail with respect to the DEM, a heterogeneous FEM is adopted. Such a model is able to account both to block and joint elastic deformability and material nonlinearity; however, for simplicity, such nonlinearity is considered only at joint level. Differently with respect to DEM, this model allows to obtain more

accurate information on structural behavior in terms of stresses and strains; on the other hand, it requires a large computational effort with respect to the DEM, due to the larger number of degrees of freedom involved in the analysis, which depend on the mesh refinement adopted. The heterogeneous FEM here considered was specially introduced for modelling masonry [15] and, among the different FEs proposed by the element library, standard four-node quadrilateral elements are adopted for representing masonry blocks, whereas zero-thickness four-node interface elements are adopted for representing the joints between the blocks. Plane strain hypotheses are adopted, and blocks deformability is accounted by means of their elastic modulus E_b and Poisson's ratio ν_b , whereas zero-thickness interfaces are characterized by a normal stiffness k_n and a tangential stiffness k_s , together with joint tensile strength, cohesion and friction ratio.

Arch reinforcements can be modelled with one or two-dimensional elements and zero-thickness interfaces can be used for connecting the elements for the bricks with those of the reinforcements. However, a simpler approach for modelling reinforcements can be the application of standard or elastic restraints on the degrees of freedom involved by the contact with the reinforcement.

Analytic Model. The analytic model adopted here has been already introduced by authors in a contribution dedicated to the collapse mechanisms of masonry domes [16]. The model envisages a method for the limit analysis of the arch, based on the kinematic approach, characterized by an algorithm that defines the position of the hinges, along the arch intrados and extrados, generated by a kinematic mechanism that may be activated by the minimum collapse multiplier of the live load F . As well known, the activation of a collapse mechanism of the arch is characterized by the formation of four hinges. The position of two of them is considered fixed along arch extrados (Fig. 2a), in particular the last one (X_4, Y_4) is supposed to be at the base of the arch on the opposite side with respect to the position of the live load, which is typical of masonry arches; whereas the second one (X_2, Y_2) is supposed to be matching the application point of F . The position of the other two hinges (X_1, Y_1) and (X_3, Y_3) is assumed to vary along the intrados. Each hinge is defined by an angle α_i , with $i = 1, \dots, 4$, hence angle α_1 defines a portion of arch A_1 , which is not involved in the mechanism, whereas the other angles allow to define portions A_2, A_3 , and A_4 involved in the mechanism (Fig. 2b). The dead loads represented by the self-weight P_i of each arch portion involved in the mechanism and, if present, the self-weight of arch fill, are defined by point forces applied at each portion center (Fig. 2c).

Fig. 2 – Generic collapse mechanism for a circular arch: (a) hinge position; (b) arch portions involved in the collapse mechanism; (c) graphical determination of the displacements.

The supposed mechanism allows to determine both graphically and numerically the displacement of the application point of each force of the model; then, the virtual work principle may be written, and the minimum multiplier of the live load F can be determined by defining a set of values for each unknown angle, namely $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_2 < \alpha_3 < \alpha_4$:

$$\lambda_{\min} = \min \left\{ \left[\sum_{i=2}^n P_i \cdot v_i(\alpha_1, \alpha_3) \right] / [F \cdot v_F(\alpha_1, \alpha_3)] \right\} \quad (1)$$

Numerical tests

A well-known case study originally introduced by Orduna [13] and already adopted for the validation of other numerical models [14] is considered. The masonry arch (Fig. 3) has a span $S = 5.0$ m, rise $R = 2.5$ m, thickness $a = 0.3$ m and width $s = 1.0$. It is made of 31 voussoirs and it is covered by a back-fill up to a height $H = 3.0$ m, which represents only a further dead load for the structure. Masonry volumetric weight ρ is equal to 20 kN/m^3 , whereas back-fill volumetric weight is equal to 15 kN/m^3 . The other mechanical properties of the blocks and the joints between the blocks are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 3 – Geometry of the unreinforced masonry arch [13] (a) and of the reinforced masonry arch (b).

Table 1 – Mechanical properties of the masonry arch

Blocks	Elastic modulus	E_b	10000 [MPa]	Joints	Normal stiffness	k_n	2400 [N/mm ³]
	Poisson's ratio	ν_b	0.2		Shear stiffness	k_s	1000 [N/mm ³]
	Density	ρ	20 [kN/m ³]		Friction ratio	μ	0.75

Unreinforced masonry arch. The masonry without any reinforcement is subject to its self-weight, to arch fill self-weight and to an increasing vertical force F acting along arch extrados, at one quarter of the entire arch span (i.e. $d = 1.25$ m in Fig. 3) from arch left end.

Fig. 4a shows the load-displacement curves obtained with the three models adopted, together with the ultimate load obtained with the limit analysis solution performed in [13, 14], and equal to 18 kN. The ultimate load obtained with the DEM is equal to 18 kN, and that obtained with the FEM is equal to 17.8 kN. The ultimate load given by analytic model turns out to be equal to 17.77 kN, and it is obtained with angles $\alpha_1 = 24^\circ$, $\alpha_3 = 149^\circ$. All the models are in good agreement with themselves and with the reference solution. Fig. 5a shows the collapse mechanism obtained with the DEM, which is characterized by the development of four hinges. The mechanism obtained with DEM is in excellent agreement with that obtained in [13] and hinge positions turn out to be alternately along arch intrados and extrados. The same mechanism is also obtained with the analytical model. Fig. 5b shows the collapse mechanism obtained with the FEM, which turns out to be in good agreement with that obtained with DEM and analytically, even if the opening of the third hinge is less evident, due to the deformability of the blocks.

Reinforced masonry arch. The masonry arch is then strengthened by applying a reinforcement along the extrados, from the left support up to the 7th block, with a reinforcement horizontal projection length r equal to 0.60 m (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 4b shows the load-displacement curves for the reinforced arch obtained with the different numerical models. The effect of the reinforcements increases the ultimate load of the arch; the DEM reaches an ultimate load equal to 22 kN, whereas the ultimate load obtained with the FEM is equal to 20.75 kN. In this case in the analytic model, the reinforcement of the arch is considered by increasing the arch portion A_1 not involved in the collapse mechanism: $40^\circ < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2$. With a first hinge position $\alpha_1 = 40^\circ$ and a third hinge position quite close to that obtained with the unreinforced case, $\alpha_3 = 149^\circ$, the analytic limit load multiplier turns out to be equal to 23.19 kN. Fig. 5c shows the collapse mechanism obtained with DEM. As expected, the new mechanism is characterized by

four hinges alternated along arch intrados and extrados, with the first hinge on the left that appears at the end of the reinforcement and of the other hinges are placed similarly to the unreinforced case. Fig. 5d shows the collapse mechanism obtained with the FEM, which is quite close to that obtained with DEM, with an evident hinge opening at the reinforcement end and under the applied load.

Fig. 4 – Load-displacement curves for the unreinforced masonry arch (a) and the reinforced one (b).

Fig. 5 – Collapse mechanisms of the unreinforced (a,b) and reinforced (c,d) arch obtained with DEM (a,c) and FEM (b,d).

Conclusion

In this work, the behavior of masonry arches, without and with reinforcements, has been studied by means of three numerical models: an existing DEM, originally introduced for modelling regular masonry and extended to the case of masonry arches; a heterogeneous FEM for obtaining more accurate results and validate DEM results; and an analytic model based on the kinematic theorem of limit analysis, adopted as a further benchmark for the previous results. The three models turned out to be accurate and in excellent agreement with themselves and with existing solutions, even if the heterogeneous FEM is more deformable and the corresponding ultimate load is slightly smaller than that obtained with the other models with the reinforced arch case. The analyses performed with DEM allowed to obtain collapse mechanisms where hinge formation was evident, also in the load-displacement curves characterized by sudden slope variations until the final horizontal branch highlighting the occurred collapse. Mechanisms also turned out to be in quite good agreement with those obtained analytically and represented by the angles of the unknown hinges along arch intrados or extrados. Further developments of this work will take into account existing case studies of unreinforced and reinforced arches tested in laboratory [7, 8], in particular, the simplified approach

here adopted for representing the behavior of arch strengthening will be better investigated, and more accurate properties for restraining elements and arch-reinforcement interfaces will be adopted.

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